

Dellingr Phase 2: Deliverable 2

First Pilot project: Usage analysis

Dellingr team *

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1 Executive Summary

The NeIC Dellingr project is investigating how a lightweight framework for sharing High Performance Computing (HPC) resources ¹ can be implemented between participating countries. ² This document gives a description of the first Dellingr pilot ³ that placed users on shared high performance computing resources within the participating countries. This document consists of the following sections:

- Purpose of the document – defines the scope of the deliverable and its intended audience;
- Dellingr pilot – describes the background and procedures used in the resource exchange pilot.
- Dellingr pilot usage – presents the resource exchange numbers
- Dellingr Pilot User Experience – presents the responses of the users of their experience in the pilot.
- Dellingr second pilot – the overall goals of a follow-up pilot are presented.
- Summary – summarizes the experiences of both the users and providers of the shared resources.

2 Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this document is to describe, to NeIC and the national providers the experiences of the national providers and users in the first Dellingr resource sharing pilot. This document is to be used as a basis for further discussions on the HPC resource sharing leading to a general agreement. It can also be used to show the changes required for a second Dellingr pilot that would deploy a prototype of the proposed resource exchange model, exchange rates and common framework. The recipients of this document are the national providers and NeIC.

3 Dellingr Pilot

In the Dellingr project Phase 1 a resource-sharing pilot was proposed and approved, see Phase 1 Delivery Object 1 [1]. The first pilot was a test to ensure that resources could be efficiently shared across the national boundaries of: DK, EE, FI, IS, NO ⁴, SE. Norway does, with Finland, participate in the NeIC Nordic Languages Processing Laboratory as detailed in [2]. Also, the procedures for the national HPC providers were tested as given in the Dellingr Phase 1 Deliverable 2 [3]. The initial amounts of resources donated to the pilot are given in [3], these were subsequently increased in some cases ⁵.

The representatives of the National e-infrastructure providers informed research communities and groups within their countries via email about the existence of the pilot and opportunity to apply for computing resources. The rule for this pilot is that prospective applicants had to be eligible to run on their national e-infrastructure provider resources in order to be considered to run abroad. These potential users were directed to an explanatory page on the NeIC Dellingr welcome page [4] which led to a Typeform application page [5].

The process for users to apply for resources in this pilot was as follows:

¹A resource is defined in this instance as the compute, network and storage infrastructure of a shared system.

²Currently this includes the Nordic countries and Estonia.

³“pilot project” - activity planned as a test or trial. From <https://www.thefreedictionary.com/pilot+project>

⁴Norway did not directly contribute resources to the Dellingr pilot but Norwegian researchers were granted access to pilot resources.

⁵Estonia joined in December 2017 with approximately 1M core hours.

1. Users applied to the Typeform page to gather basic information on the project: Name, contact details, affiliation, subject, resource request, special resources required;
2. The Typeform page forwarded the request to the Project Manager (PM);
3. PM consulted the national provider reps to host the request in a country other than originator;
4. PM consulted whether shared resources had been consumed fully;
5. If agreed, the user was put into direct contact with the national provider;
6. User applied using the national provider procedure(s);
7. User (or their delegate) gains access to shared resource and is then free to setup and run their software.

The accounting of shared resources was done by the national providers using their own procedures. Overall, the first Dellingr pilot served 20 users with 2.4M core-hours granted over 9 months.

There were 23 applications in total, 3 were not eligible for the pilot as their hardware requirements could not be met or the application originated from a non-eligible institution. In more detail: one application required a minimum of 1.5 TB of RAM and originated from an institute funded by a different ministry than that of their national e-infrastructure provider. In this case they were not, at the time, eligible to run on their national e-infrastructure provider and therefore could not “avoid” the rules by running in another country under this pilot. Two applications were received from a government-funded research institute (not academic) and therefore did not meet the criteria of the pilot to run abroad.

4 Dellingr Pilot Usage

In the Dellingr Pilot, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, and Sweden contributed resources as shown in the Table 1. Research groups from Norway were eligible but Norway provided no resources.

Host/Guest	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden	Total
Denmark	x	117	100	150	150	75	592
Estonia	200	x	250			50	500
Finland			x	250	100	200	550
Iceland	50			x		50	100
Norway					x		
Sweden	200		500			x	700
Total	450	117	850	400	250	375	2442

Table 1: The number of kcore-hours hosted by each national provider participating in the Dellingr pilot. The horizontal totals are the total number of kcore-hours applied for by each country. The vertical totals are the kcore-hours hosted by each country.

The Dellingr first pilot call was launched in July 2017 and the last applications were received in January 2018. These figures summarize the extent of the Pilot:

- 21 applications were received;

- 3625 kcore-hours were requested by the applicants;
- 18 projects were accepted;
- 2442 kcore-hours were granted to the accepted projects;
- 898 kcore-hours were consumed by the projects.

Only three applications were rejected. In one case the resources available did not match the request: the application requested a larger memory (RAM) than available in the contributed resources. Two of the rejected applications were from a non-academic research institute which was not eligible.

In total, 67 % of the requested resources (kcore-hours) were granted and 82 % of the requested resources by the accepted applications.

Not all accepted projects used their quota, and only five projects used all or most of it. Seven projects did not use their quota at all. It is often difficult to predict the needed CPU time on to complete a research task, and sometimes you have a choice on platforms where you can produce the results. This phenomenon of non-used resources is well-known in shared e-infrastructures and is mitigated by over-subscription. Normally e-infrastructures are over-subscribed by allocation committees in order that resources are not idle. The over-subscription rate is usually based on experience and the Dellingr first pilot did not employ this technique.

The resources actually consumed used by the pilot participants in Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, and Sweden are presented in Table 2. In Table 2, it can be seen that the consumed and hosted kcore-hours are not the same for

Host/Guest	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden	Total
Denmark	x	0	72	148	0	0	220
Estonia	200	x	0			0	200
Finland			x	57	0	204	261
Iceland	1			x		0	1
Norway					x		
Sweden	140		77			x	217
Total	341	0	149	205	0	204	899

Table 2: The amount of actual used kcore-hours hosted by each national provider participating in the Dellingr pilot. The horizontal totals are the total number of kcore-hours consumed by each country. The vertical totals are the kcore-hours hosted by each country. A value of "0" indicates that core-hours were allocated but not consumed.

each country but this is not considered an issue over such a short-term pilot.

All the user project applications to the pilot and their resource requests are described in Table 3 in the chronological order of arrival. As Estonia became later involved in the pilot, the cases where it is either giving or receiving resources came in late in the pilot. Norway had only two project applications but the accepted Norwegian participants finally used no resources.

5 Dellingr Pilot User Experience

In order to get feedback on the Dellingr pilot user experience the following questions were sent to user that applied for resources:

1. How easy was it to get the account on the "foreign" shared resources?

Project Title	From	To	Requested kcore-hours	Granted kcore-hours	Used kcore-hours
Deep learning speech enhancement with blind features	FI	DK	100	100	72
De-novo assembly of reindeer rumen metagenome data	FI	–	250	–	–
Containers and virtual machines for HPC	NO	FI	100	100	0.0
Parallel glacier modeling using scientific workflows	IS	FI	200	200	6.8
PolymerBlends	DK	IS	150	50	0.013
Interactions between Hadley Cell and storm tracks in aquaplanets	NO	DK	250	150	0
p14-ARF and Bcl-xL interactions as a new target in familial melanoma	DK	–	250	–	–
How sphingolipids regulate the structure of a key autophagy protein?	DK	–	150	–	–
Combined quantum mechanics molecular mechanics	IS	FI	50	50	50.3
3D topology optimization of field enhancing nanostructures for upconversion	DK	SE	200	200	139.6
Effective theory of structure formation	IS	DK	250	150	148
Amplification and nonlinear mitigation with phase sensitive amplifiers	SE	DK	75	75	0
Atomic scale insight into sulphide-induced corrosion of copper	SE	FI	250	150	154.0
A framework for improving water resources data using hydraulic modelling	SE	IS	50	50	0
The role of synaptic cell membrane in dopamine entry in its receptor	FI	SE	250	250	77.1
Improving ultrashort electron and laser pulses: Towards nanocameras for electron motion pictures	FI	SE	250	250	
Real-time path-integral Monte Carlo	FI	EE	250	250	0
DFT calculations of ionic liquids	EE	DK	250	117	0
Neural machine translation for morphologically complex languages	SE	EE	50	50	0
Tryggve use case for supporting Nordic colorectal cancer (CRC) collaboration	SE	FI	50	50	50.0
Atomistic origins of material loss from surfaces	DK	EE	200	200	200
Total			3625	2442	897.813

Table 3: All received Dellinger Pilot applications and the amount of requested, granted, and used kcore-hours in the order of arrival. The column “From” gives the country of origin of the application and the column “To” the hosting country (DK=Denmark, EE=Estonia, FI=Finland, IS=Iceland, NO=Norway, SE=Sweden).

2. Did you need application support? If so, did it work well?
3. Did you have licensing issues? Were they solved?
4. Other comments.

Most of the participating groups answered the questions, and eventually 12 sets of answers were received. According to most pilot participants the user accounts were created smoothly. However, we have to remember that they were created manually after receiving the user information. In a couple of cases the setup took a month, which is too long for a these small projects. For a larger number of applications the process should be made more automated. To open user accounts in Sweden, the participants needed to provide copies of their passports, and it was suggested to use digital signatures instead.

Moving data around and between the national provider and the data repository of the participant may become an issue if data amount is excessive.

Licensing was not considered an issue in most cases as most participants used open software, or the participants had their own licenses. Some software library issues were solved by the application support.

Application support is definitely needed as there were several mentions on this. There was only one mention that the support would have been better if it were local. They suggested to have a system for swift follow-up of support issues and helping projects. Probably the local helpdesk addresses were not communicated clearly.

In general, the feedback was very positive, and this type of exchange of Nordic e-infrastructure resources was considered useful.

5.1 Answers to the User Query

All the answers to the user query are listed below according to the country of origin.

5.1.1 Denmark

Title: *3D topology optimization of field enhancing nanostructures for upconversion* (Host National Provider: Sweden)

1. The whole Dellingr application process was VERY easy, smooth, and fast. To get the account at LUNARC, we had to send copies of our passports by mail. This was a bit tedious, but no major problem. A digital signature of some sort would have been easier. The web-based registration at LUNARC was also very easy and the two-stage sign-in with SMS codes works well.
2. We have been in contact with support a few times regarding MPI jobs, allocation of nodes, and SMS codes for login. In all cases the support was excellent and the issues were resolved quickly.
3. No, we have only used open source software and our own code.

Title: *PolymerBlends* (Host NP: Iceland)

1. Very easy and administration free. However, there is some practical overhead when running simulations different places and moving data around.
2. No. I know the module system, and compiled LAMMPS myself.
3. No issues. LAMMPS is GPL open source.

Title: *Atomistic origins of material loss from surfaces* (Host NP: Estonia)

1. It was not that easy to setup the connection and It took us almost a month to setup everything, which is understandable as some activities were needed from our university. But we received great and fast support from people at Estonia and once it (was) established, everything works perfectly fine so far.
2. Yes, especially at the beginning, we have lots of issues (from both sides) with connecting to the server. But they have a very comprehensive help and manual at Estonia and helped us to resolve all issues step by step.
3. Since we are working with open source software, we have not any issue with licensing.
4. Thank you for your follow-up. In general, we are very happy with the Dellingr platform and it has been super useful for us. It helps us to run systematic and large scale atomistic simulations. We already started to prepare two publications based on these simulations.

It is a great idea to have these shared facilities. In particular, as I recently joined to my university, this computational facility was a vital help to establish and continue my research. I am really looking forward to future of Dellingr platform.

5.1.2 Estonia

Title: *DFT calculations of ionic liquids* (Host NP: Denmark)

1. Account creation was easy, unfortunately haven't done anything more so far.
2. N/A
3. N/A

5.1.3 Finland

Title: *Real-time path-integral Monte Carlo* (Host NP: Estonia)

1. Creating the account and, as of later, authenticating was well documented and guided by the foreign administration. The user and privilege hierarchy had to be created out of scratch, but that never became a problem.
2. Our application demand was not prominent. There was one issue with an incompatible library, but it was promptly solved upon request. Overall, the administration has been eager to look after our needs.
3. We do not use licensed software in this project.

Title: *The role of synaptic cell membrane in dopamine entry in its receptor* (Host NP: Sweden)

1. The application required some paperwork such as passport scan and application form have to be sent by mail and password has been provided by phone call. Despite this everything has been very simple and fast.
2. All the required information has been sent at beginning of the granted period. They were very detailed and easy to follow.
3. No we did not have any licensing issues. We used only open sources software.

5.1.4 Iceland

Title: Parallel glacier modeling using scientific workflows (Host NP: Finland)

1. It was very smooth.
2. Since the scientific applications we are using were developed by CSC, therefore application support was very quick. Even if there is an update or issue in the application it was dealt without much delays.
3. Apart from the scientific application, we are using a scientific workflow management system and HPC middleware called UNICORE. We wanted to have it installed on CSC resources. The administrative staff was very supportive and helpful on installing UNICORE and made it available for our use case.
4. N/A.

Title: Effective theory of structure formation (Host NP: Denmark)

1. It was quite easy and efficient.
2. I did need support for the initial login. The support was excellent with concise and prompt answers.
3. I did not have any licensing issues

Title: Combined quantum mechanics molecular mechanics (Host NP: Finland)

1. When the project started the CSC admins contacted me beforehand and provided me with the necessary credentials upon request (within the same day). I'd rank that very easy.
2. Yes. In order to install my software, I required information regarding numerical libraries available on the cluster. I contacted CSC support and was provided with the necessary information on the same day (actually within the hour) to complete my task (compiling my code). This worked out extremely well.
3. All software used operate under the GNU license. Hence, no issues.
4. As far as I'm concerned this worked out perfectly.

5.1.5 Sweden

Title: Neural machine translation for morphologically complex languages (Host NP: Estonia)

1. Very easy.
2. No need so far.
3. No issues.

Title: Atomic scale insight into sulphide-induced corrosion of copper (Host NP: Finland)

1. It was a very streamlined process - very much adapted to "urgent needs" as we had.
2. The people at the center were very responsive and supportive.
3. It was the usual VASP licensing but it went through quite quickly. All in all we are very happy with the outcome and the way you have set up the application and granting process.

4. We really did appreciate the opportunity very much.

Title: Atomic scale insight into sulphide-induced corrosion of copper (Host NP: Finland)

1. Easy, very helpful.
2. Yes. They tried to be helpful, but the project dragged on as it is more difficult to gain a full understanding when one is not close.
3. No
4. Maybe a system for swift follow-up of support issues and helping projects to deliver

6 Dellingr Second Pilot

The second pilot call will be carried out in order to achieve the technical goals of the project.

The technical aspects to consider in the second pilot:

- Information: gather the same set of information as the Typeform page of the first pilot;
- AAI: the users should be strongly authenticated to the system;
- Digital signatures. Test digital signatures for service provider – user agreement;
- Accounting: the consumption of the shared resources should be measured in a common place;
- Benchmarking: the benchmarks of the shared resources should be displayed in a common place; see as an example: <http://snic.se/resources/compute-resources/aurora/>
- Reporting: How the resources have been used? Any publications resulting? This information should be gathered to a common place.

The second pilot should be similar in time as the first, 9 months of computing time.

6.1 Changes and Modifications

The Second Pilot will use a framework (Waldur) to gather the information above as required by all participating countries. The Virtual Allocation Committee can be fulfilled by a project group member from each country where we assume that the pilot applications have already been forwarded by a national committee.

Mailing physical copies of passports to ensure the identity of users is slow and cumbersome; this has been required by the Swedish sites. We will propose to investigate whether the use of a scanned passport saved in a cryptographically signed PDF document (i.e. copies of passports) ⁶ would be acceptable as a replacement for a physical photocopy.

Also GDPR compliant descriptions of the processing of personal data and agreements of data exchange between the sites have to be made for the Second Pilot phase.

⁶<https://acrobat.adobe.com/content/dam/doc-cloud/en/pdfs/overview-of-electronic-signature-law-in-the-EU.pdf>

7 Summary

Overview of results

The First Dellinger Pilot was successfully implemented and valuable feedback of it was gathered during the setup and execution of the user projects and also afterwards.

It can be seen from Table 1 that the researchers were fairly evenly distributed across countries. Denmark hosted computing from all other countries. This is mainly an artifact of the manual allocation process in which a maximum distribution was sought in order to gather all possible experiences for the national e-infrastructure provider hosts.

Most of the response by the participants was very positive and they felt that this kind of resource exchange is fruitful. The procedures for researchers, from another country, to gain access i.e. account and quota creation were generally seen as smooth and fast. This was also appreciated as these computing allocations were relatively small and these projects could proceed without much delay. One item of note was the requirement in one country to mail a physical copy of the PI passport to a central location.

Improvements

One group noted that as the users of the resources are located far away from the actual resource, the need for extensive documentation and manuals is even more prominent than for users situated close to the resource, both from the pure user perspective but also with regards to the application process. This is something that will be addressed in the second pilot. Accounting could be improved by using a common framework to collect usage information. Also, an acceptable method to send a passport copy digitally using a common resource sharing framework will be investigated.

One issue that can be noted from Tables 1 and 2 is that the actual amount of kcore-hours consumed by users is far less than allocated. The accounting for a longer-term resource sharing system must be able to identify users that have historically not used allocations and mitigate for this fact. In Table 3, it can be seen that some users indeed used their allocation completely. Again, a longer-term resource sharing effort must be able to identify such efficient users and possibly reward them.

Conclusion

Overall, we can conclude that there are no technical barriers to share computing e-infrastructure across borders. As can be seen with this limited pilot there are no barriers to short-term limited e-infrastructure resource sharing. The legal, policy and financial impediments for long-term e-infrastructure resource sharing must be addressed.

Appendix: Publications

List of publications, submitted or to be submitted at time of writing, that can be attributed to computing time from this pilot:

- Applicant: IS Host: FI <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2018-158>.
- Applicant: SE Host: FI “On the nature of the cathodic reaction during corrosion of copper in anoxic sulfide solutions” to be submitted.
- Applicant: DK Host: EE “On the origins of third-body particle formation during adhesive wear” submitted to Elsevier journal "Wear".

- Applicant: DK Host: EE “Wear of AFM tips: from atom to debris” to be submitted to journal "Nature Material".
- Applicant: IS Host: FI “Combined quantum mechanics molecular mechanics”.

References

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